

A Tribute to the Legacy of Prof. Nina F. Thornhill in Plant Abnormal Behavior Analysis

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Abstract: Few researchers worldwide have pushed the state of the art of plant abnormal behavior analysis in process industries as Prof. Nina F. Thornhill. Her numerous and significant contributions published in renowned journals and international conferences have undoubtedly inspired a large number of researchers to pursue projects in this field. Proudly, I can regard myself as one of them, since Nina's work significantly influenced my research on topology-based plant abnormal behavior analysis. Part of the developments derived from that research appears in my doctoral dissertation for which I had the great honor to have Prof. Thornhill as a reviewer. This paper presents and dedicates those developments to her.

Keywords: Fault detection and diagnosis, plant abnormal behavior analysis, alarm management

1. INTRODUCTION

Plant abnormal behavior analysis is concerned with the study of faults affecting production systems in industrial facilities. Its applications include, among others, root cause analysis, controller performance assessment, and alarm management (Chiang, *et al.*, 2001, Yang, *et al.*, 2012).

Few researchers worldwide have explored this topic in such a level of detail as Prof. Thornhill has. Her work has not only shed light on the solution of complex industrial diagnosis problems but also has inspired a large number of individuals to pursue research projects in this area. As a matter of fact, I am one of them.

Back in 2012 when I joined the Institute of Automation Technology at the Helmut Schmidt University (HSU) in Hamburg, under the supervision of Prof. Alexander Fay, I ran into a number of Prof. Thornhill's contributions on root cause analysis and alarm management (e.g., Thornhill *et al.*, 2003, Bauer *et al.*, 2005, Bauer and Thornhill, 2008, Thambirajah *et al.*, 2009, Di Geronimo *et al.*, 2011, Schleburg, *et al.*, 2013) that truly captured my research interest. I was delighted both by the scientific rigourousity and the industrial applicability of the proposed methods.

After a thorough review of more of her papers, I was convinced that this line of research could make a significant impact in industrial practice and I decided this was the topic I wanted to explore in my doctoral dissertation. I expressed my interest to Prof. Fay and soon enough he got me involved in a cooperation research project on plant topology engineering with ABB and with Prof. Thornhill's chair at Imperial College London.

As part of this cooperation, I had the opportunity to co-supervise together with Prof. Fay and Prof. Thornhill two master theses of HSU's students during their semester abroad at Imperial. Some of the insights derived from those works were extended in a joint publication on the derivation of diagnostics models based on formalized process knowledge (Arroyo, *et al.*, 2014). During this period, I got

to know Nina a bit better. I learned she was not only a professional of remarkable knowledge; she was also a genuinely kind and inspiring person with whom working together was a pleasure. I remember I hoped back then that was not the last time we would work together.

While I continued exploring the topic of topology-based plant abnormal analysis by incorporating connectivity, semantics, and underlying first principles of plant components to data analysis, my research got even closer to Prof. Thornhill's research scope. Prof. Fay accordingly suggested asking Prof. Thornhill if she would be interested in being the second reviewer of my dissertation. To my great honor, Prof. Thornhill expressed her interest in the topic and accepted the proposal.

Fig. 1. Doctoral examination in Hamburg. From left to right: Prof. Nina F. Thornhill, Dr. Esteban Arroyo, Prof. Alexander Fay, Prof. Markus Bause

On June 9, 2017, I successfully completed my doctoral examination. Fig. 1 shows a picture of the evaluation committee and me on that day. Thanks largely to the scientific advice of Prof. Fay and Prof. Thornhill, this dissertation got me awarded the 2019 HSU research prize. As a way of expressing my gratitude, I would like to dedicate in this paper some of my dissertation developments, specifically a new topology-based plant abnormal behavior analysis method, to Prof. Thornhill.

The remainder of this contribution is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the fundamental notions of the proposed method. Section 3 explains the conceptual artifacts sustaining the underlying approach. The detailed implementation of the overall diagnosis concept is presented in Section 4, and its feasibility as a basis to support alarm management and root-cause determination is demonstrated in Section 5. Experimental results are analyzed in Section 6, and Section 7 concludes the paper with a brief summary.

2. PROPOSED METHOD FOR PLANT ABNORMAL BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS

The proposed method for plant abnormal behavior analysis is based on a graph-scheme, which compartmentalizes plant topology and process knowledge into modular components associated with plant equipment. From a functional perspective (Bunte, *et al.*, 2016), this method falls into the class root cause diagnosis approaches, whereas based on the used a priori knowledge; it can be classified as a hybrid approach (Iyun, 2011), since it incorporates characteristics of both quantitative and qualitative model-based methods (Venkatasubramanian, *et al.*, 2016a, b, c). The following three key-notions sustain the underlying diagnosis concept:

- Disturbances are transported across the plant by a defined set of material and information propagation carriers.
- Certain equipment and process characteristics (static and dynamic propagation-related factors) influence the behavior of disturbances propagating across the plant.
- The occurrence of multiple process alarms may be an indicator of disturbance propagation. Analyzing the causality between alarms can, therefore, support the determination of potential root-causes.

Based on such notions, the method performs a systematic evaluation of process causalities by combining topology and process information for the discovery of disturbance propagation paths linking observed alarms. Such a procedure comprises two main parallel tasks: (a) the event-triggered generation of dynamic causal digraphs (DCDGs), i.e., modular causal models interconnected based on plant connectivity information, and (b) the recursive consultation of a propagation look-up table (PLUT) containing general and process-specific information for establishing updated causalities within and among plant components.

In the sequel, the main conceptual artifacts of the proposed approach, i.e., the dynamic causal digraph and the propagation look-up table, are presented.

3. CONCEPTUAL ARTIFACTS

3.1 Dynamic causal digraph

A DCDG is a modular causal model depicting relationships between process variables by capturing the first-principle structure of the underlying system without providing detailed equations for the modeled causal relations (Chiang *et al.*, 2001). DCDGs are essentially based on the concept of signed directed graphs (SDGs); however, unlike typical SDGs, dynamic causal digraphs extend and modify certain

aspects concerning causal descriptions, graph structure, and model generation. The following subsections discuss in detail the main differences between SDGs and DCDGs.

3.1.1 Causality and temporal description capabilities

Although SDGs are a suitable approach to causal modeling, their capabilities for detailed process descriptions may result insufficient in some cases. Consider for instance the SDG segment illustrated in Fig. 2, which depicts some of the causal relations occurring in an exothermic reactor. As it is known from first principles, the cooling water (CW) flow causes a suppression effect (-) on the process temperature, whereas the temperatures of the reactant feeds produce a reinforcement influence (+) on the same variable. In the event of a disturbance, the behavior of the process temperature will largely depend on whether the CW flow or the reactants temperatures have the stronger influence, as well as on the time constants of the underlying causalities. Such relations, however, cannot be represented through SDGs, as these neither quantify the extent to which a node affects its successor nor describe temporal causalities.

Fig. 2. SDG segment of a chemical reaction process

Another limitation of SDGs is their incapability to model qualitative relationships between process variables that cannot be simply described as “suppression” or “reinforcement” effects. Take as an example the case in which the magnitude “feed composition” is modeled as a node in a SDG. One may naturally expect that the composition has a direct influence, among other variables, on the process temperature, implying thereby the existence of a direct arc in the causal graph. Nevertheless, due to the vagueness of the term “feed composition” –understanding this as the concentrations of different chemical components in the feed– it is not possible to clearly determine whether the relation is of type “-” or “+”. While the increase of the concentration of a certain component may imply an increase of process temperature and thus a “+” relation, the same increase involves the reduction of the concentration of another component, which in turn can be seen as the cause of the observed temperature increase and therefore suggests a “-” relation. Although one could argue that this problem can be solved by modeling the concentration of every feed component as a separate node in the SDG, this may result in an undesired explosion of the graph size. For several purposes, it might be of interest to keep certain causal relations at a “ambiguous” level. It follows that a new causal state to characterize such process relations is required.

In view of the aforementioned shortcomings, the dynamic causal digraph extends the description of directed arcs by incorporating the quantitative magnitudes influence strength or intensity (ϕ) and expected time delay or lag (τ), as well as by adding a new qualitative causal state (0) to characterize ambiguous causal relationships between nodes. As discussed in more detail later on in this section, influence strengths allow providing a simple quantitative approximation of the influence of a node on its successor, while expected time delays enable the description of temporal relations between nodes. The addition of these new descriptive features is formalized in the following definition:

Let $G = (V, E, \phi, \tau, \lambda, \Delta)$ be a graph defined by two non-empty sets namely, the vertex set V (nodes) and the edge set E (directed arcs), with $E \subseteq V \times V$, such that $\phi : E \rightarrow a \in [0, 1]$, $\tau : E \rightarrow t \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\lambda : E \rightarrow \{+, 0, -\}$ represent the strength, expected time delay (lag), and forward influence of an edge, and $\Delta : V \rightarrow \{+, 0, -\}$ describes the qualitative status of a vertex as given by:

$$x_{vi} - \tilde{x}_{vi} > \varepsilon_{vi} \text{ then } \Delta(vi) = "+" \quad (1)$$

$$|x_{vi} - \tilde{x}_{vi}| < \varepsilon_{vi} \text{ then } \Delta(vi) = "0" \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{x}_{vi} - x_{vi} > \varepsilon_{vi} \text{ then } \Delta(vi) = "-" \quad (3)$$

where \tilde{x}_{vi} is the set point (steady-state value), and ε is a given threshold.

Based on the above definition, the arc consistency criteria of the DCDG can be formulated as follows: An arc is said to be consistent if the product of the cause node, the directed arc, and the effect node is positive, i.e., $\Delta(v_{+n}) \cdot \lambda(v_n) \cdot \Delta(v_{-n}) = "+"$, whereas an arc is regarded as ambiguous if its value is zero, i.e., $\lambda(v_n) = "0"$. In general, disturbances may propagate both through consistent and ambiguous arcs, although penalization clauses may be applied to the latter due to the associated propagation uncertainty (Section 4.3).

The proposed model extensions can significantly increase the expression capabilities of the causal graph while keeping its structure still simple and independent of complex mathematical models. This is one of the main advantages of dynamic causal digraphs compared to previous approaches incorporating e.g., transfer functions (Leyval *et al.*, 1994) differential equations (Montmain and Gentil, 2000), and further mathematical models (Aslund *et al.*, 2007) into bond graphs, fault trees, and other causal graphs.

3.1.2 Defined set of model variables

Unlike SDGs, which only specify the structure of the causal graph but not its variables, dynamic causal digraphs define a specific set of model variables, so-called propagation carriers, to describe the process causalities occurring within and among components in a process. As depicted in Fig. 3, considered propagation carriers are divided into two main classes, i.e., *Material* (subdivided in *Pressure*, *Flow*, *Level*, *Composition*, and *Temperature*), and *Information* (subdivided in *SensorSignal*, *ControllerSignal*, and *ActuatorSignal*).

The consideration of a specific set of variables pursues uniforming the modeling of process systems at a level of detail suited for the analysis of disturbance propagations. While taking into account a larger number of process variables would increase the capabilities of the DCDG for depicting more detailed causalities, this would result in larger models –harder to maintain and interpret– as well as in the need of more computational resources and longer execution times. Accordingly, the defined set of propagation carriers has been chosen to be specific enough to enable the causal modeling of most chemical processes in industrial applications, and compact enough to allow for fast discovery of propagation paths.

Fig. 3. Considered propagation carriers in process systems

3.1.3 Graph-tabular structure

The consolidation of process relevant data through sensible visualization can significantly facilitate process diagnostics (NAMUR NA96, 2017). With the aim of allowing for a structured visualization of process causalities and potential propagation paths, dynamic causal digraphs in contrast to typical SDGs, are organized in rows and columns (see Fig. 4). In this structure, rows represent plant assets organized by topological connectivity, whereas columns symbolize considered propagation carriers, respectively: *Composition* (C), *Temperature* (T), *Pressure* (P), *Flow* (F), *Level* (L), *SensorSignal* (SS), *ActuatorSignal* (AS), and *ControllerSignal* (CS).

A DCDG node embodies the state of a given variable (column) within a certain plant asset (row), indicating whether the variable is in normal or upset condition (e.g., too low or too high). DCDG edges, in turn, describe the qualitative and quantitative causal influence of a node on its successor as well as the expected lag of the underlying cause-effect relation. As discussed later on in Section 3.2, the estimation of causal and temporal values considers process information, such as component and process properties, and experiential knowledge or heuristics. Columns corresponding to propagation carriers of type material (T, P, F, Q, L) are populated with nodes embodying plant assets in contact with the material flow (e.g., pumps, pipes, and tanks), whereas columns representing propagation carriers of type information (SS, AS, CS) are populated with nodes accounting for devices within control

Fig. 4. Example of DCDG corresponding to the single-phase open tank system with level control depicted in Fig. 5

loops (i.e., sensors, actuators, and controllers). Note here that only those components aimed at storing liquid volumes, such as vessels, contain nodes in the *Level (L)* column.

For the connectivity of the nodes within rows and columns, three types of links are distinguished, namely: *Directed Link (DL)*, *Component Inherent Link (CIL)*, and *Information Link (IL)*. As depicted in Fig. 4, a *DL* (black arrow) relates nodes in different rows and represents the existent physical connection among plant assets. A *CIL* (light blue arrow), in turn, connects nodes within a given row and symbolizes existing bonds between variables in a determined piece of equipment due to a physical principle; for instance, the relation temperature-pressure in a two-phase closed tank (due to the ideal gas law). Finally, an *IL* (purple arrow) symbolizes the communication path between elements in a control loop, and can connect different rows and columns. Unlike the previously defined DCDG causal properties –i.e., strengths, lags, and qualitative causalities– link types are not modeled as edge attributes, as they are implicitly defined by the coordinates of the related nodes in the graph.

The consideration of link types allows capturing the semantics of the different connections occurring in the process, which enables filtering searches and prioritizing diagnosis results based on detailed data queries (Section 4.3). During the generation of DCDG models, required connectivity links are created by consulting the connectivity information contained in the plant topology model and a propagation look-up table (Section 3.2).

3.1.4 DCDG model generation

In contrast to SDGs, which are typically static models built once for a modeled process, dynamic causal digraphs are

generated in an event-triggered basis, i.e., an individual DCDG is dynamically constructed when a process disturbance (signalized by alarms) is detected or alternatively upon request of the user. The particular DCDG for that event considers up-to-date information of the process and its assets, thus allowing an accurate description of the plant abnormal situation.

Topology information (e.g., connectivity, flow directionality, and static characteristics of plant assets) required during the generation of the DCDG is extracted from a plant topology model as described in Arroyo *et al.*, 2017, whereas dynamic process data can be collected directly from a control system (e.g., DCS or SCADA), a process historian, or a simulation environment.

The linkage between topology information and causal process knowledge (i.e., first principles, heuristics, and static and dynamic process data) is accomplished by storing the causal relations of plant components such as heat exchangers, pumps, and reactors as templates in a knowledge repository or library (Section 3.2). When one of these components is identified during model generation, the corresponding causal relations of the asset are consulted in the library and instantiated in the DCDG. Should causal relations contain expressions or functions in terms of plant or process data (e.g., types, dimensions, or states), the algorithm retrieves this information from the topology model by exploiting fit-to-purpose data access methods, specifically AFDD PDS, PKS, and PS model facets (Arroyo *et al.*, 2017). Once all causal relations have been evaluated and instantiated, the resulting component causal models (modules) are interconnected based on the connectivity information described in the topology model. In order to

illustrate the dynamic generation of the DCDG, consider the following brief example.

In the plant section depicted in Fig. 5, a flow disturbance, concretely an unusual flow increase, is detected in Pipe002 by the flow sensor F204 (highlighted in red color). An automatic diagnosis is started and accordingly a DCDG for the specific event is generated by instantiating the causal models of every component in the process and linking them according to the system connectivity.

Fig. 5. Plant section. Flow anomaly detected by sensor FIR204. Single-phase liquid open tank with level control

The corresponding Dynamic Causal Digraph is depicted in Fig. 4. From it, two possible consistent propagation paths are discovered, namely:

1. $FIR204(SS) \rightarrow Pipe003(F) \rightarrow Valve001(F) \rightarrow Pipe002(F) \rightarrow Tank001(P) \rightarrow Pipe001$
2. $FIR204(SS) \rightarrow Pipe003(F) \rightarrow Valve001(F) \rightarrow LC201(CS) \rightarrow LIR201(SS) \rightarrow Tank001(L) \rightarrow Pipe001$

The first found propagation path indicates the disturbance could have been produced due to an increase in the outflow of Pipe001 causing a rise of Tank001 pressure and ultimately an increase of the outflow propagating along the subsequent plant components (Pipe002, Valve001, and Pipe003) through the flow carrier. The second propagation path also presumes the disturbance was originated due to an alteration in the outflow of Pipe001, which produced an increase of the Tank001 level and consequently a raise of the outflow propagating to Pipe003 caused by the control loop action (LIR201, LC201, V001). Despite suggesting two different propagation paths, one containing only material flow carriers and the other both material and information flow carriers, both discovered propagation hypotheses pinpoint an upset in the flow of Pipe001 as the potential root-cause of the anomaly.

For the ranking or prioritization of discovered propagation paths, the overall strengths of every path are computed. This procedure is systematically executed by multiplying the strength values of every edge (ϕ_i) in a given path. Resulting overall strengths are sorted in order of magnitude, which allows prioritizing and filtering paths based on defined strength thresholds.

Given the existence of multiple alarms caused by plant anomalies, the same disturbance propagation concept can be applied to group related alarms and classify observed alarms as causal and consequential. In general, attending causal

alarms requires specific operator counteractions, whereas the clearance of consequential alarms does not. In virtue of the underlying causal relation, consequential alarms will be automatically suppressed after the root of their causal alarm has been found and attended. Therefore, the proposed concept may significantly facilitate the required actions of plant operators when facing plant abnormalities.

3.2 Propagation look-up table

The propagation look-up table (PLUT) is a reusable and cumulative data repository or library containing component-specific connectivity links and expressions for the estimation of their respective causal and temporal properties. Aligned with the modular vision of causal models described by Di Geronimo *et al.*, (2011), and Yang *et al.*, (2012), the PLUT embodies a collection of templates or modules representing the causal behavior of plant assets and process units, which are instantiated and connected during the generation of dynamic causal digraphs based on connectivity and process data.

Table 1. General structure of a PLUT

Component	Coordinates	Causal Properties ($\phi/\tau/\lambda$)	Rationale
$Component_1$	X_a, Y_b	$IF : Condition_1$ $(\phi_1/\tau_1/\lambda_1)$	$Explanation_1$
...
$Component_n$	X_a, Y_b	$IF : Condition_n$ $(\phi_n/\tau_n/\lambda_n)$	$Explanation_n$

As depicted in Table 1, the PLUT comprises four columns, namely *Component*, *Coordinates*, *Causal properties* ($\phi/\tau/\lambda$) and *Rationale*.

The column *Component* contains the list of plant assets or process units for which connectivity templates are available ($Component_1, \dots, Component_n$). The granularity of stored templates is variable and can go from single components, e.g., pumps, tanks, and valves, to complex equipment combining multiple components such as washing and separation units.

The column *Coordinates* specifies the external and internal causal relations or connections of every stored component. Coordinates have the form (X_a, Y_b) , where X and Y refer to the source and destination carriers (i.e., $T, P, F, C, L, SS, AS, CS$) linked by a given connection, and sub-indices a and b make reference to the inlet and outlet ports of the component associated by the causal relation. By way of illustration, the ordered pair (F_{i-1}, P_i) describes the connection between the inlet flow of a component and its outlet pressure. Note that in this structure, the outlet of a component corresponds to the inlet of the succeeding component.

The column *Causal Properties* ($\phi/\tau/\lambda$) describes the quantitative and qualitative causal and temporal characteristics of a connection (strength, lag, and causal effect) by providing values and expressions such as constants and simple functions for their estimation. Expressions might contain *IF-statements* constraining the

existence and properties of causal relations to specific component and process characteristics, such as the device type or operation state (e.g., “on”, “off”, “open”, or “close”). The definition of $(\phi/\tau/\lambda)$ values is not constrained to a specific methodology. In fact, it can be carried out by following different approaches such as abstraction of expert know-how, heuristics, or process data analysis (Yang *et al.*, 2014). Values may be estimated, for instance, based on plant component characteristics, empirical observations, or statistical analysis of process data (Bauer *et al.*, 2005).

The column *Rationale* presents a description of the first-principle or heuristic rule justifying the existence of a given connection (edge) and optionally a comment regarding the values or expressions assigned to the causal and temporal characteristics of a given edge. Its fundamental aim is to facilitate knowledge management within the PLUT.

Table 2 illustrates a fragment of a propagation look-up table describing one of the causal relations a volume object may have under specific conditions. Here, the graph coordinates, the respective causal and temporal expressions, and the rationale for the modeled causal relation can be retrieved by look-up. When a volume object (e.g., a reactor) is identified during model generation, the algorithm systematically consults the causal relations of this type of device in the PLUT, verifies that the current causal relation applies to the particular object by evaluating the specified *IF-statements*, and instantiates it in the DCDG with the respective causal and temporal values.

Table 2. Fragment of a PLUT

<i>Component</i>	<i>Coordinates</i>	<i>Causal Properties</i> $(\phi/\tau/\lambda)$	<i>Rationale</i>
Volume	(F_{i-1}, L_i)	IF: 2-phase, open volume, liquid flow inlet $(.99/.1 * d/+)$	Volume level is dictated by accumulation of liquid. A flow disturbance has a direct and significant effect in the level carrier. This effect is not instant. The underlying lag is determined, among other factors, by the dimensions of the volume object.
...

d: Volume diameter in meters. Time lag τ in hours.

From the knowledge management perspective, the PLUT can be regarded as an extensible data repository based on the concept of aggregation, i.e., new and refined knowledge can be added in accordance to the current information requirements or data availability. Such a knowledge base can be defined for a set of standard plant assets, i.e., a vendor-independent catalogue of plant devices commonly found in process facilities (e.g., generic valve, generic tank, and generic centrifugal pump).

This property allows the methodology to be system-independent, and guarantees its effective and intuitive applicability in projects of different nature. Notice, however, that the PLUT also allows the addition of vendor-specific catalogues or plant-specific assets. This fact, nevertheless, does not go against the philosophy of non-system dependency but rather constitutes a resource to refine the

precision and accuracy of the evaluation functions, if required.

The knowledge modularity offered by the propagation look-up table alongside the dynamic nature of the DCDG allows overcoming one of the main drawbacks of SDG-based fault diagnosis, i.e., the high effort required for information collection and model maintenance (Yim *et al.*, 2006, Chiang and Braatz, 2003). As modules can be easily extended, updated, or exchanged in complete independence of the causal graph itself, the tedious inspection process required for the update of large models can be avoided. In turn, updated knowledge can be automatically and systematically transferred from the PLUT to those instances in the causal graph affected by the underlying changes.

4. INTEGRATED DIAGNOSIS CONCEPT

Previous research has shown that the use of causality information between process alarms allows identifying propagation paths and thus supporting operators during root-cause analysis (Hollender and Beuthel, 2007, Yu and Yang, 2015). Aligned with this notion, the proposed diagnosis method uses alarms as key disturbance indicators for the discovery of propagation paths based on the concepts of dynamic causal digraphs and propagation look-up tables. However, as an initial requisite for involving alarms in causal disturbance analysis, specifically in propagation paths searching and filtering, a direct association or mapping between alarms, measurements, and plant components is needed. The following subsections discuss how this mapping can be automatically generated based on available information sources, and explain how integrated alarm data, plant information, and process knowledge are exploited within the proposed path searching and filtering strategies.

4.1 Mapping process alarms to plant assets

In order to relate alarm-based root-cause hypotheses to process signals and ultimately to plant assets, a mapping between related instances is required. In this contribution, this mapping is created by analyzing the connectivity between sensors, alarm functions, and components in the topology model. By way of illustration, consider the schematic of Fig. 6a in which a process vessel (S001), a pressure sensor (PIR116), and two alarm functions (PAL116 and PAH116) are depicted.

The topology model corresponding to this schematic contains the connections $S001 \rightarrow PIR116$, $PIR116 \rightarrow PAL116$, and $PIR116 \rightarrow PAH116$. The analysis of these links allows assigning the described alarm functionalities to the pressure measurement as well as relating these alarms to the process vessel, as shown in the left-hand side of Fig. 6b. Such a representation can be further transformed into a structure matching the status convention used in alarm logs. Supposing that in the used convention, the statuses of low and high level alarms are indicated as *LO_ALM*, *LO_LO_ALM* and *HI_ALM*, *HI_HI_ALM*, Algorithm 1 can be used to generate the required associations. Fig. 6b illustrates the mapping generated for alarms with one and two status levels.

In many occasions, however, no explicit graphic symbols are used in the process schematic to depict alarm functions. Instead, these are described by additional characters in the tags of the measurements to which they are associated.

Fig. 6. Plant section. Flow anomaly detected by sensor FIR204. Single-phase liquid open tank with level control

The tag “LICA+-”, for instance, indicates a level controller with value indication (LIC) and high/low alarm functions (A+-). In these cases, the mapping is derived from the syntactical analysis of the tags –based on regular expressions– alongside the consideration of the connectivity between plant assets and instruments. Once the alarm functionalities have been identified, Algorithm 1 can be applied to generate the required mappings.

Algorithm 1. Mapping process alarms to plant assets

For all alarm functions:

If (alarm function is of type “L”)

Create 1...n low alarm functions such that:
n=1: LO_ALM, n=2: LO_LO_ALM...

If (alarm function is “H”)

Create 1...n high alarm functions such that:
n=1: HI_ALM, n=2: HI_HI_ALM...

Where $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is a user-defined parameter indicating the number of low and high alarm status levels in the log.

As for other common alarms and warnings not specified in process schematics (e.g., valve and pump malfunctions), default alarm functionalities might be associated to actuation devices in the topology model with the respective failure statuses used in the alarm convention. By way of illustration, all controlled valves in the process might be assigned a standard alarm functionality “failure”.

4.2 Path search algorithm

Based on the alarm mapping information, alarms can be associated to specific elements in the DCDG; hence, traversing the graph allows the discovery of propagation paths linking observed alarms during a plant disturbance. The path finding algorithm can be configured to search for paths beginning at an element, ending at an element, or between two elements in the graph. This enables operators and process experts to query information on three types of

causal results, namely: possible consequential alarms derived from a potential causal alarm, potential causal alarms for a chosen consequential alarm, and possible propagation paths between two given alarms.

Provided an initial element, propagation paths are computed by iteratively adding new elements until a stop criterion is met. For a new element to be added in the current path, the following criteria must be fulfilled:

1. *Maximum path length*: The length of a path cannot exceed a maximum number of allowed elements. Empirical observations suggest that long propagation paths tend to be spurious and are less likely to reveal the actual source of an anomaly. Limiting the maximum path length to a moderate value allows increasing diagnosis accuracy and reducing computation time.

2. *Minimum overall strength threshold*: Because each edge in a path has a baseline strength, it is possible to keep track of the overall strength of a growing path after each new edge is added. If a given path is deemed implausible early on during computation, it is neither pragmatic nor computationally efficient to keep adding further elements, since the path only becomes less plausible as new elements are added.

3. *Number of times a given node can be used in a path*: Due to recycles and control loops in the process, a given DCDG element might appear more than once in a propagation path. Limiting this value to a low threshold allows preventing undesired path loops.

4. *Number of times a particular edge can be used in a path*: Similar to the previous criterion, limiting this value to a given maximum prevents the generation of spurious paths with unwanted inner loops.

The generation of propagation paths between two selected elements provides the basis for alarm causal analysis and alarm grouping. This process is conducted by testing each pair of alarms bi-directionally, i.e., each tested as potential causal and consequential alarm. However, in order to prevent unnecessary computations, it is recommendable to pre-process analyzed alarm logs by removing chattering alarms (ISO 18.2, 2009). As discussed by Kabir *et al.*, (2013) and Rodrigo *et al.*, (2016), such alarms can be simply filtered by setting a threshold for the minimum allowed time between two occurrences of the same alarm, i.e., two alarm instances with the same alarm tag and status (see alarm log in Table 3). Thus, if the elapsed time between two alarm occurrences is shorter than the given threshold, the second alarm is to be removed.

Table 3. Fragment of a common alarm log

Time In	Alarm Tag	Area	Description	Status	Priority
08-Nov-16 22:30:15:10	L7061	CA38	Level Wash Column	HI_ALM	Critical
08-Nov-16 22:31:13:32	P7063	CA38	Pressure Wash Column	HI_HI_ALM	Critical
...
08-Nov-16 22:39:16:40	L7061	CA38	Level Wash Column	HI_ALM	Critical

Once the analyzed log has been initially filtered, a search algorithm computes potential paths between every pair of alarms by considering graph connectivity and predefined stop criteria, as well as by applying penalization and filtering strategies (Section 4.3). Search results are stored in form of an alarm connectivity matrix (ACM) describing the directional causality among inspected alarms. If the algorithm finds a feasible propagation path connecting one alarm to another, this result is stored as a “1” in a specific row and column of the ACM, meaning the alarm associated with that row was found to cause the alarm associated with the respective column.

	A1	A2	A3
A1	0	1	1
A2	0	0	1
A3	0	0	0

	A1	A2	A3
A1	0	1	0
A2	0	0	0
A3	0	0	0

	A1	A2	A3
A1	0	0	0
A2	0	0	0
A3	0	0	0

	A1	A2	A3
A1	0	1	0
A2	0	0	1
A3	1	0	0

Fig. 7. Example ACMs for an alarm log with 3 entries. Colors illustrate alarms belonging to the same alarm group

The analysis of alarm connectivity matrices allows identifying alarm groups as well as classifying observed alarms as causal and consequential. Sequences of interconnected alarms in the matrix reveal alarm groups, in which any alarm without a found cause is regarded as causal, and, by the same token, any alarm caused by others is regarded as consequential. Fig. 7 presents four abstract examples of ACMs. Here, the following alarm groups and alarm types are inferred:

- **ACM a)** → 1 alarm group $AG_1 = \{A1, A2, A3\}$; causal alarms $\{A1\}$; consequential alarms $\{A2, A3\}$.
- **ACM b)** → 2 alarm groups $AG_1 = \{A1, A2\}$, $AG_2 = \{A3\}$; causal alarms $\{A1\}$, $\{A3\}$; consequential alarms $\{A2\}$.
- **ACM c)** → 3 alarm groups $AG_1 = \{A1\}$, $AG_2 = \{A2\}$, $AG_3 = \{A3\}$; causal alarms $\{A1\}$, $\{A2\}$, $\{A3\}$; consequential alarms $\{\emptyset\}$.
- **ACM d)** → 1 alarm group $AG_1 = \{A1, A2, A3\}$; causal alarms $\{\emptyset\}$; consequential alarms $\{A1\}$, $\{A2\}$, $\{A3\}$.

The causal results derived from the above ACM examples account for a large amount of common causalities found in typical plant alarm logs. The first example, for instance, illustrates the best-case scenario in which all current alarms belong to the same alarm group and can be explained by a single causal alarm. The second example, in turn, shows different alarm groups with different causal alarms. The case in which all current alarms are unrelated and belong to different groups is illustrated in the third example. Finally, the fourth example presents the scenario in which despite the existence of alarm causalities, no causal alarm can be

inferred due to reciprocal causal relations among certain process variables.

Scenarios as the one illustrated in the last example are in general difficult to diagnose. However, in certain cases their occurrence may be mitigated by adjusting the defined search stop criteria, particularly the number of times given nodes and edges can be used in a path. While this strategy proves useful in dealing with the effect caused by control loops and process recycles, it cannot mitigate the effect of reciprocal relations caused by inherent links in a component. An example for this is the relation between temperature and pressure in a closed vapor tank. By the above strategy, neither variable could be identified as causal alarm if both alarms were triggered, for there will always be an alarm that can be inferred as a cause of the other. In such cases, an exception must classify both alarms as causal, provided no other alarm is found to cause them.

It is worth noticing that causal analysis as described above can only pinpoint causal alarms, but not specific fault root-causes. However, based on identified alarms groups and respective causal alarms, the task of operators and process experts in finding fault root-causes is substantially simplified owing to the achieved reduction of the possible solution space. Alternatively, obtained causal results can be further processed by rule-based and data-driven approaches to draw automatic inferences relating causal alarms and root-causes. For example, if the flow in and out of an open tank are measured, observing tank level to be the causal alarm of the observed abnormal situation would lead to automatically identifying a tank leak as fault root-cause based on the analysis of flow behavior.

4.3 Path penalization and filtering strategies

Aiming at reducing the number of potential causal hypotheses resulting from the DCDG analysis, penalization and filtering clauses are applied to discovered propagation paths before diagnostic results are shown to the operator. Proposed strategies combine both qualitative and quantitative data on aspects regarding process deviations and temporal behavior, as well as types of variables and propagations paths. On account of flexibility, strategies are designed to be independent of each other, which allows users to select the penalization clauses and the respective order in which they should be applied depending upon the monitored system and the particular monitoring objectives.

4.3.1 Penalization based on deviation sign and magnitude

Dynamic process data is incorporated both qualitatively and quantitatively to penalize potential propagation paths based on the sign and magnitude of observed process deviations. As the signs of influence of each edge (λ_i) along a path are known, a given path can be ruled out when the observed deviation of any variable along the path does not match the predicted sign, i.e., when the path is found to be qualitatively inconsistent. Exceptions to this criterion apply in paths containing ambiguous edges and unmeasured nodes, cases in which a different penalization strategy aimed at dealing with uncertainties is used (Section 4.3.3).

In addition, it is desirable to remove paths including variables that are qualitative consistent, but do not deviate significantly enough from steady-state to propagate a disturbance. The magnitude of deviation should be accordingly considered to introduce further penalties, which may push unlikely paths below the threshold for consideration. Yet, there is a challenge to maintain general applicability at this point, because determining when a signal has deviated sufficiently to impact other signals is an arbitrary decision typically based on an expert notion. In developing an arbitrary penalization strategy that works for a specific process, there is no guarantee for similar effectiveness in other applications. To deal with such an obstacle, the penalization strategy must incorporate process-specific knowledge.

Process metrics such as absolute or relative deviations are dependent on several arbitrary factors like units. However, there is a source of information containing process-specific expert judgments about deviations: the alarm limits. Here, it is presumed that limits are set by process experts and control engineers in a reasonable way, such that they are triggered when process variables deviate “significantly”. If the deviation from steady-state values is normalized by the low-to-high alarm range, then a $\pm 100\%$ deviation will almost certainly be significant, while a $\pm 5\%$ will likely not be responsible for disturbance propagations –except in the case of controlled variables. Accordingly, penalization factors, based on e.g., heuristics and statistical data, are defined for different normalized deviation magnitudes. Table 4 presents an example of a deviation-based penalization scheme.

Table 4. Quantitative penalization of propagation paths based on deviation magnitude. Example of possible deviations ranges and associated penalty factors ($p_1 \leq p_2 \leq p_3 \leq p_4 \leq 1$)

Normalized absolute deviation	Penalty factor
0 % – 10 %	p_1
10 % – 25 %	p_2
25 % – 50 %	p_3
$\geq 50\%$	p_4

While the above penalization concept may filter a large number of spurious propagation paths, caution is recommended when applying this strategy, since wrongly set alarm limits have been reported among the most common causes of alarm floods in process industries (Wang *et al.*, 2015).

4.3.2 Penalization based on time

As expressed in (4), the time delay $|T_A - T_B|$ between a given pair of related alarms A and B can be estimated as the sum of the lags T_{dyn} , T_{thr} , and T_{cs} resulting respectively from the system dynamics, the defined alarm thresholds, and the alarm-related parameters of the control system (e.g., filter time constants and sampling period). Time delays modeled in the DCDG, however, only provide a first approximation of the lags related to system dynamics (T_{dyn}) and do not consider those delays introduced by other factors.

As a consequence, the accumulated time delay of a propagation path linking two given alarms cannot be used to judge whether these are related by comparing observed and expected time delays in absolute terms. Nevertheless, the consideration of time lags predicted by the DCDG provides an intuitive basis to penalize those causal hypotheses with time delays differing from expected values in relative terms.

$$|T_A - T_B| \approx T_{dyn} + T_{thr} + T_{cs} \quad (4)$$

Provided $T_{dyn} \leq |T_A - T_B|$, the proposed penalization concept divides the time frame given by the magnitude of the delay between two alarms $|T_A - T_B|$, in n discrete time bins, and locates both the observed time delay T_{obs} and the expected time delay T_{exp} in the resulting bins based on their magnitude. Naturally, the observed time delay T_{obs} will always lie in the n^{th} bin, as its magnitude is equivalent to the size of the considered frame (i.e., $T_{obs} = |T_A - T_B|$). However, the expected time delay T_{exp} , which is equivalent to the lag caused by the system dynamics and predicted by the DCDG (i.e., $T_{exp} = T_{dyn}$), may lie in any of the n bins. The distance between observed and expected time bins is penalized by defined factors p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{n-1} , setting stronger penalties to those bins lying far away from each other, i.e., $p_1 \leq p_2 \leq p_{n-1} \leq 1$. In this way, those alarms with time delays differing significantly –in relative terms– from those predicted by the DCDG are penalized. If the accumulated strength of potential propagation paths was already low, the time penalization may force those paths to be rejected or ranked as less likely. The number of time bins and the magnitudes of the respective penalization factors may be defined based on the statistic analysis of previous process alarms or by considering heuristic rules. Fig. 8 illustrates the proposed time penalization concept.

Fig. 8. Representation of the time penalization concept

4.3.3 Penalization of ambiguous edges and unmeasured variables

As previously explained in this section, the deviation-based strategy (Section 4.3.1) penalizes those paths found to be qualitatively inconsistent. Yet, due to the existence of ambiguous arcs and unmeasured nodes in the DCDG, in some cases paths cannot be simply regarded as consistent or inconsistent, but instead must be deemed ambiguous. While disturbances may propagate through ambiguous paths, the dynamics of such propagations cannot be verified through process data, as certain required measurements are not available. In view of the underlying propagation uncertainty, a given penalty factor p is applied to each ambiguous edge and unmeasured node in the path. Thus, the overall strength

of paths containing multiple ambiguities may be ranked as less likely or forced below the defined acceptance threshold.

4.3.4 Filtering based on type of propagation carrier

The description of different connection links allowed by the DCDG (i.e., direct, component inherent, and information links) enables the application of a further filtering strategy based on semantics.

By applying high-level queries of the type “*search for propagation paths including/excluding x type of connection links*”, for instance, this strategy makes it possible to analyze the individual effect of information and material connections on process disturbance propagations. A possible application of this strategy is foreseeing during detailed troubleshooting; for example, to analyze if a given control loop was responsible for propagating a certain fault.

4.4 Visualization of diagnostic results

After all plausible paths have been identified and filtered, diagnostic results are presented to the operator for visualization. To that end, the algorithm generates four different representations of inferred causalities: (i) a colored DCDG highlighting those nodes which triggered alarms as well as the edges found to link these nodes, (ii) a graph-based representation of the process schematic highlighting those components found to be affected by the disturbance propagation, (iii) a colored connectivity matrix depicting the connectivity between alarms and the resulting alarm groups, and (iv) a list of ranked propagation paths with respective causal alarms. The user may choose which of these representations is more convenient to visualize the information required for his current task.

5. VALIDATION

The proposed method was validated on the analysis of alarms and disturbance propagations in the TEP model controlled with Luyben’s plant-wide regulatory control scheme (Luyben, 1996). The TEP specifies 28 process faults, from which 7 were found to trigger multiple alarms and accordingly were used for testing. In addition, 11 anomalies caused by valve failures were considered during experimental trials (see Appendix H in Arroyo, 2017). The resulting 18 different plant and process disturbances were used as base ensemble for the generation of test scenarios including single and multiple faults. During conducted tests, the monitoring focus was set on the analysis of disturbances propagating along main process streams, omitting explicitly process utilities. The goal of the diagnostic procedure was to group related alarms triggered during fault scenarios, identifying in each case the respective causal alarm. The following sections describe the used experimental setup as well as the obtained diagnostic results.

5.1 Experimental setup

5.1.1 Information sources

As previously discussed in Section 4, the presented diagnosis concept combines plant topology, static and

dynamic process information, and first physical principles for the discovery of disturbance propagation paths linking observed process alarms. During validation, this information was extracted from three main sources: a formalized plant topology model, a process simulation model, and a propagation look-up table.

a. Plant topology model

The TEP integrated topology model presented in Arroyo (2017) was used as connectivity and directionality information source, as well as data repository containing *dimension-specific*, *component-specific*, and *process-specific* information applied for the evaluation of system causalities.

During the generation of dynamic causal digraphs, relevant information in form of attributes in the topology model was retrieved through the proposed fit-to-purpose data access methods, specifically the AFDD PDS, PKS, and PS facets (Arroyo, 2017). By consulting the respective *Timebehavior* property of every retrieved attribute, the algorithm correctly differentiated between static and dynamic information. While the content of static attributes was directly collected from the topology model, dynamic attributes were only interpreted as references to the actual data content found in another data source, in this case, the simulation model.

b. Simulation model

The MATLAB TEP simulation model originally proposed by Downs and Vogel, (1993), and recently revised by Bathlet *et al.*, (2015) was used to reproduce the system dynamics occurring during plant and process anomalies. Process signals referenced by attributes with *dynamic Timebehavior* properties in the topology model were retrieved from the simulation environment and used during the search and penalization of potential disturbance propagation paths.

c. Propagation look-up table

The propagation look-up table presented in Appendix I of Arroyo, (2017) was used as fundamental repository of process causalities. As causal connections and qualitative relationships among variables and components in the PLUT stem from sound first physical principles, they are virtually valid for any chemical process. However, strength values and time delays (lags) presented in this particular PLUT have been tailored specifically for the TEP based on previous observations and heuristics.

On account of simplicity, these values were defined as constants and not as general mathematical expressions. The reason for this relies in the fact that the ultimate aim of the presented method is not to delve into the definition of detailed process causal equations, but to present a new modular causal analysis approach whose level of detail can be adapted based on available causal information.

5.1.2 Configuration of process alarms

Since no standard alarms have been reported in the literature for the Tennessee Eastman Process, custom alarms were

configured in the simulation model by considering normal and limit process operation values reported in Downs and Vogel, (1993). In the interest of counting with high monitoring resolution, two alarm status levels, i.e., ALM_LO_LO, ALM_LO, ALM_HI, and ALM_HI_HI, were defined for every measured signal in the process main streams. In the particular case of composition measurements collected at the same process location, measurements were lumped together into a single concentration alarm functionality, which is triggered when one of the single thresholds is exceeded. For the purpose of the trials, no actuator failure alarms were configured.

5.1.3 Definition of path search and penalization thresholds

a. Path search thresholds

As discussed in Section 4.2, four numeric criteria are iteratively evaluated during the search for propagation paths. The following values were respectively used during conducted tests: maximum path length = 10, minimum overall strength threshold = 0.2, number of times a given node can be used in a path = 1, number of times a particular edge can be used in a path = 1.

b. Penalization settings

During validation, three penalizations strategies were applied for filtering potential paths. Table 5 lists those strategies and summarizes their specific parameterization.

Table 5. Penalization strategies used during conducted experimental tests

Penalization strategy	Criteria	Penalty factor
Deviation magnitude	Normalized absolute deviation	
	0 % - 10 %	$p_1 = 0.1$
	10 % - 25 %	$p_2 = 0.6$
	25 % - 50 %	$p_3 = 0.8$
	> 50 %	$p_4 = 1.0$
Time delays	Number of bins	
	5	$p_1 = 0.1$
		$p_2 = 0.3$
		$p_3 = 0.6$
$p_4 = 0.8$		
Uncertain paths	Penalized items	
	Ambiguous arcs and unmeasured nodes	$p_1 = 0.95$

5.2 Diagnosis results

By using the described experimental setup, the proposed diagnosis method was tested on the analysis of 30 fault scenarios including single, double, and triple disturbances. Appendix A reports the obtained diagnosis results. As can be observed, the report shows the fault number as listed in Appendix H of Arroyo, (2017), the type of fault (i.e., single faults vs. multiple faults triggered simultaneously or in time intervals), the immediate process variable affected by the anomaly, the number of alarms triggered during the abnormal situation, and the position of the causal alarm in the analyzed log. In addition, it presents the result (success,

partial success, or failure) of the diagnosis procedure, as well as the type of error (i.e., false positive (P) vs false negative (N)) for those cases in which the method failed in detecting true causalities or assigned false alarm relations.

Fig. 9. Example ACMs for an alarm log with 3 entries. Colors illustrate alarms belonging to the same alarm group

Experimental results presented in Appendix A revealed 19 successful detections, 6 partial detections, and 5 mis-detections. As summarized in Fig. 9, these absolute figures evidenciate that the algorithm successfully or partially successfully diagnosed 83 % of the analyzed cases, while failed at finding the causal alarm for 17 % of the fault scenarios. The causes of partial and failed detections are various: detailed accounts on these cases are presented in the next subsection.

5.3 Analysis of partial and failed detections

5.3.1 Partial detections

As previously mentioned, partial detections are those in which more than one causal alarm hypothesis is generated for a given alarm group. During experimentation, the analysis of the following six fault scenarios resulted in partial detections.

- IDV 5: Due to existence of reciprocal alarm pairs, four potential causal alarms were identified for this scenario.
- IDV 1,5: IDV1 was correctly diagnosed, however, three possible causal alarms for IDV5 were suggested due to the existence of reciprocal alarm pairs. In both cases, the alarm groups were correctly identified.
- IDV 4,6: Root IDV6 was correctly diagnosed, but six candidates for a potential second causal alarm were proposed due to the combined effect of control loops and process recycles.
- XMV 1: With the D feed stream completely cut off, the pressure in the reactor feed pipeline (mixing zone) decreased significantly, thus causing an important increase of the flow exiting the stripper headspace. As no pressure sensor exists in the mixing zone, the causal algorithm diagnosed both the D feed flow and the stripper outflow as potential causal alarms.
- XMV 10: Another scenario in which the lack of a pressure sensor in the mixing zone caused the detection of more than one hypothesis, specifically three potential causal alarms.
- XMV 11: Due to the existence of reciprocal alarm pairs, four causal alarms were diagnosed for this scenario.

The analysis of the aforementioned accounts allows concluding that the main causes for partial detections are the existence of reciprocal alarm pairs (e.g., temperature and pressure) and the lack of certain process measurements. The first cause can be approached by using complementary process knowledge, for instance in form of expert rules, whereas addressing the second requires additional instrumentation, or, alternatively, the application of soft sensors and data-driven analysis algorithms. Due to the involved costs of acquiring additional instrumentation, to date the use of complementary methods seems to be a more suitable approach; however, the continuous growth of installed sensors in process plants suggests that the lack of measurements will be no longer an issue in near future, especially in the frame of Industry 4.0 (Wee *et al.*, 2015).

5.3.2 Failed detections

Failed detections refer to those cases in which the algorithm did not succeed at determining the correct alarm group(s) or at finding the respective causal alarm(s). Among failed detections, two specific types are distinguished: false positives (P) and false negatives (N). The former type designates cases in which unrelated alarms were grouped, while the latter refers to scenarios in which related alarms were not associated. From the 5 failed detection cases observed during conducted experimental tests and reported below, 3 were false positives and 2 false negatives.

- IDV 2: False negative. Due to alarm thresholds, only two sensors triggered alarms, i.e., FIR103 (A+C feed flow) and FIR115 (Purge flow). These measurements are located on opposite sides of the process. The connection between alarms can be detected, but the maximum allowed path length must be extended from 10 to 20, and there must be no penalty for unmeasured nodes.
- IDV 1,13: False positive. IDV1 significantly alters the compositions throughout the entire process, thus the slow drift in reaction kinetics could not be clearly observed. As a consequence, only IDV1 was identified as a causal alarm.
- IDV 4,5: False positive. IDV4 was correctly identified, but IDV5 was interpreted as an effect of IDV4. The short pipelines of the TEP and the resulting lack of significant transport delays make the simultaneous temperature spikes in the reactor (R003) and the separator (S012) consistent both with a disturbance only caused by IDV4, and with a fault caused simultaneously by IDV4 and IDV5.
- XMV 4: False negative. The algorithm was unable to find the connection between the reduction of A+C feed flow and the increase in stripper (E005) temperature. The actual cause of the observed temperature increase is unclear, as the stripper pressure dropped while inlet feed temperature decreased. A potential explanation for this phenomenon is a drastic composition change in the stripper leading to a shift in VLE, which in turned caused rapid condensation and heat release. The observed slight increase of the stripper level supports this hypothesis.
- XMV 1,2,3: False positive. When the D feed fails before the A and E feeds (15 min interval), the latter disturbances cannot be diagnosed because the former fault alters the magnitudes of the A and E feeds making the respective flow alarms look as consequential.

The accounts above evidenciate that the main cause of failed detections is related to the propagation of faults across the process, which makes the algorithm interpret causal alarms as consequences of other causal alarms due to process connectivity and consistent qualitative behavior. This effect is particularly observable in the TEP as no transport delays between process units are modeled, preventing the algorithm from penalizing certain causalities based on observed time lags. In order to address this drawback, data-driven methods (e.g., non-linear series analysis) can be applied on identified signals to verify the causality or independence between specific alarms.

6. ASSESSMENT

Section 5 demonstrated the applicability of the proposed diagnosis method on the determination of alarm groups and the diagnosis of causal alarms. As revealed by the obtained experimental results, the method demonstrated a strong performance recognizing or partially recognizing 83 % of the analyzed fault scenarios and failing at diagnosing only 17 % of the cases. Considering the simplicity of the used expressions for causal properties (i.e., influence strengths and time lags), the little manual effort required for the implementation of the concept in the analyzed system, and the overall high complexity of the TEP, obtained diagnosis results are regarded as highly positive.

Detailed accounts on cases in which the algorithm did not succeed at fully diagnosing plant abnormal situations alongside provisions on how to address current drawbacks were provided. Overall, it was concluded that with additional instrumentation and/or complementary use of rule-based and data-driven methods, the diagnosis reliability of the proposed concept could be further enhanced. In the remaining of this section, the main advantages and limitations of the approach are summarized.

6.1 Advantages

Compared to existing approaches in academia and current industrial practice (see Chapter 6 of Arroyo, 2017), the diagnosis method proposed herein offers the following key advantages:

- It is based on a modular causal concept, which clearly separates the knowledge base from the model instance. This allows for effective and largely automated implementation in different processes as well as for efficient knowledge and model maintenance.
- Unlike most knowledge-based methods, the proposed approach is process-generic as it is built on topology-based relations and process causalities of general validity. Accordingly, it can be applied with little manual effort in a large number of systems within sectors ranging from chemical, nuclear, to oil and gas industries.

- It integrates connectivity, directionality, first principles, as well as component-specific and process-specific data for model generation. Therefore, causal models derived from the application of the approach are capable of representing not only the structure of the system but also the internal relationship between process variables describing its physics and chemistry. This in turn allows for granularity and accuracy during plant abnormal situation analysis.
- Due to its dynamic and event-triggered nature, it allows depicting up-to-date process causalities in contrast to other approaches based on static causal models.
- The diagnosis accuracy of the method is adjustable. Both standard plant asset catalogues of general validity as well as vendor-specific catalogues of higher precision can be stored in the PLUT and used according to the required diagnosis resolution and information availability. In addition, penalization strategies can be selected and configured by the user depending upon the particular system.
- It does not require large amounts of process data to make inference on causal alarms and consequently on potential fault root-causes.
- The approach is not sensibly affected by the existence of control loops and process recycles, as it does not delve into spectral analysis but only into the observation of qualitative signal behaviors. This, in turn, results in a further advantage: its execution does not demand high computational resources.
- It can be applied both for fault propagation analysis during fault detection and diagnosis, and in alarm management.
- In contrast to previous approaches to alarm management, it generates not only alarm groups but also identifies potential causal alarms. According to industry recommendations on process diagnostics (NAMUR NA96, 2017), this feature can significantly facilitate the task of plant operators when facing process anomalies.
- Different to existing modular causal approaches, it neither requires complex mathematical models to describe the relations between process variables, nor optimization methods and additional non-causal equations for the generation of consistent process causal models.
- It can be applied in conjunction with other methods (e.g., data-driven approaches) with overall low computation resources. Although complementary methods might demand extensive computations, applying the proposed approach as front-end during diagnosis allows filtering the number of signals that should be analyzed, thus leading to a reduction of required resources and execution times.

6.2 Limitations

Despite offering several advantages, the proposed method has certain limitations and requires some manual steps:

- It requires the definition of multiple expressions or constants for describing the causal properties (i.e.,

influence strengths and time lags) between process variables among and within components in the propagation look-up table. Likewise, it demands the specification of penalization factors for the different proposed path filtering strategies.

- It relies on dense process instrumentation for detailed diagnosis. The lack of relevant process measurements may prevent the method from finding single causal alarms in certain fault scenarios.
- It has difficulties for dealing with the detection of multiple faults, which appear to be related based on process connectivity and qualitative process behaviors. The solution of this limitation requires the application of complementary approaches such as data-driven techniques.

It is affected by the existence of reciprocal alarm pairs stemming from internal relations among variables in certain plant components. In such cases, the method does not diagnose a single causal alarm but several instead (partial detection). Overcoming this drawback requires the application of rule-based approaches incorporating deep process know-how.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In a tribute to Prof. Thornhill's legacy, this paper has presented a novel modular causal methodology for plant abnormal behavior analysis. The proposed diagnosis concept combines plant connectivity, directionality, component-specific information, first principles, and dynamic process data for the discovery of disturbance propagation paths. Due to its generic and dynamic nature, this approach is applicable in fault detection and diagnosis, and alarm management within different production systems across the chemical, nuclear, and oil and gas sectors.

Prof. Thornhill's work largely inspired this contribution, and her scientific advice was fundamental to its development. For this and for serving as a reviewer of my dissertation, I remain truly grateful to Nina and wish her all the best in her retirement. On behalf of all the scientific community, I congratulate her for her remarkable career and thank her for inspiring so many individuals with her knowledge and passion. Her legacy in plant abnormal behavior analysis and her significant contribution to science and industry will persist for many years to come.

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Appendix A. EXPERIMENTAL DIAGNOSIS RESULTS

IDV	Fault type	Disturbed variable	Alarms triggered	Causal alarm position in log	Result	Error
1	Single	Comp. A+C feed	5	1	✓	-
2	Single	Comp. A+C feed	3	1	×	N
4	Single	Temp. CW R003	51	3	✓	-
5	Single	Temp. CW C115	12	5	⊙	-
6	Single	A feed loss	24	1	✓	-
8	Single	Comp. A+C feed	8	1	✓	-
13	Single	Reaction kinetic	10	1	✓	-
1, 2	Simultaneous	See above	6	1, 2	✓	-
1, 4	Simultaneous	See above	50	2,18	✓	-
1, 5	Simultaneous	See above	18	1,5	⊙	-
1, 6	Simultaneous	See above	41	1,2	✓	-
1, 13	Simultaneous	See above	14	1,3	×	P
4, 5	Simultaneous	See above	43	4,8	×	P
4, 6	Simultaneous	See above	74	1,3	⊙	-
5, 6	Simultaneous	See above	16	1,6	✓	-
XMV	Fault type	Disturbed variable	Alarms triggered	Causal alarm position in log	Result	Error
1	Single	Flow D feed	52	1	⊙	-
2	Single	Flow E feed	60	1	✓	-
3	Single	Flow A feed	24	1	✓	-
4	Single	Flow A+C feed	44	1	×	N
5	Single	Flow K100 recycle	28	1	✓	-
6	Single	Flow Purge	5	1	✓	-
7	Single	Flow S012 bottom	13	1	✓	-
8	Single	Flow E005 bottom	17	1	✓	-
10	Single	Flow R003 CW	32	6	⊙	-
11	Single	Flow C115 CW	22	4	⊙	-
7,8	Simultaneous	See above	12	1,2	✓	-
1,2,3	Simultaneous	See above	44	1,2,5	✓	-
1,2,3	15 min interval	See above	38	1,7,14	×	P
1,3,2	15 min interval	See above	45	1,3,6	✓	-
3,6,8	Simultaneous	See above	24	1,2,6	✓	-

- Successful detections (✓) are those in which the correct alarm groups were identified and the right causal alarms diagnosed.
- Partially successful detections (⊙) are those in which more than one causal alarm hypothesis was found for a given alarm group.
- Failure detections (×) are those in which alarms were mis-grouped or causal alarms were not detected. Among failed detections, two specific types are distinguished: false positives (P) and false negatives (N).